

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Deliverable 3.5
List of Selected Proposals of 2nd Internal Call

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

BPM	Board of Programme Managers
MXX	EJP SOIL project months
WP	Work package

1. Submitted and evaluated proposals

1.1. General overview

The EJP SOIL will maximize the understanding contribution of agricultural soil towards achieving sustainability at societal, scientific, operational, and policy level. **ii) At the scientific level:** the EJP SOIL will i) develop new insights on climate-smart soil management, quantify trade-offs and synergies between agricultural production, climate change adaptation and mitigation, maintenance of soil fertility, soil health and other ecosystem services; gather new knowledge on carbon sequestration in soils under different across Europe and its contribution to climate change mitigation; improve accounting and reporting tools for emission and removals from agricultural activities. Through its knowledge framework the EJP SOIL supports knowledge development through a large number of specific research and innovation projects *via* internal (i.e. WP3 “Internal Calls”) and external EJP SOIL calls. The overall objective of the 2nd internal call has been to fund research projects open to EJP SOIL beneficiaries and linked third parties to fill research and development gaps identified by the “Roadmap for the European Joint Program SOIL”¹ and the annual work program of the EJP SOIL for year two. The call topics are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Topics of the EJP SOIL’s 2nd Internal Call.

Topic title	ID*	Number of projects and their size [#]
Plant below-ground inputs to enhance soil carbon sequestration in agricultural soils	CM1	1, medium
Effects of the soil biome on the persistence SOC storage and its drivers	CM5	1, medium
Contribution of soils to climate mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment in agroecological systems	CA4/SP3	1, large
Alleviating soil compaction in a climate change context	SP1	1, medium
The use, processing and application of external sources of organic matter to mitigate climate change and improve soil health	SP2	1, medium
Innovative techniques to monitor SOC stocks and soil degradation/restoration changes in the EU, using spectral systems/NIRS/MIRS, and other proximal sensing tools	DATA1	1, medium
Modelling soil functions and soil threats for mapping soil quality, soil functioning and ecosystem services	SE2/ INDICATORS 1	1, large
European soil biodiversity forecast towards resilient agroecosystems in response to climate change	SE4/ INDICATORS 2	1, medium
Enabling conditions for climate smart and sustainable soil policy: fair and functional incentives for ecosystem services related to climate mitigation and sustainable production	POL2/ES7	1, medium

* 2nd Internal Call Text, D3.4. EJP SOIL topic ID: CM Climate change mitigation; CA Climate change adaptation; SP Sustainable production; SE Sustainable environment; DATA Harmonizing soil information; POL Science policy interface.

[#] 2nd Internal Call Text, D3.4

¹ Keesstra et al. 2020. Roadmap for the European Joint Program SOIL: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils (Deliverable 2.4)

The WP3 Call Office published the call topics two times: a pre-announcement in M14 and the full call text in M15 (Table 2). Full proposals submission deadline was on 31st May 2021. The call office received 11 proposals addressing the call topics (Tables 1 and 3). Most project proposals were submitted by coordinators from Northern Europe (45%; Table 3), about a third by coordinators from Central and West Europe (36%) and some from Southern Europe (18%), but none of the submitted project proposals was coordinated by an EJP SOIL member from East and South East Europe. All proposals passed the eligibility check. Eligible proposals were reviewed by external evaluators between 15th July and 30th August, 2021. Final validation for funding based on external evaluation results was done by the BPM in M20 and M21. As a result, 10 project proposals were validated for funding. One project application (CA4/SP3) was rejected based on the score below the selection threshold. A brief overview of the projects validated for funding is shown in Table 4 and at the end of this section. Validated projects are supposed to start in November 2021, except MINOTAUR which will start in December 2021.

Table 2: Timeline of the EJP SOIL's 2nd internal call.

Action	Project calendar	Schedule
Call pre-announcement	M14	1 March 2021
1 st Webinar for interested applicants	M14	12 March 2021
Launch of the call	M15	1 April 2021
2 nd Webinar for interested applicants	M15	9 April 2021
Closing date for proposal submission	M16	31 May 2021
Proposal evaluation and validation	M17-20	June - September 2021
Notification letters sent to project coordinators	M21	October 2021
Grant preparation	M21	October 2021
Start of research projects	M22	November 2021
End of research projects	-/-	Depends on project size

Table 3: Number of proposals submitted per call topics; proposal coordinator; country and regions of their home country.

Topic ID	Number of applications	Proposal coordinator	European region
CM1	2	INRAE / France BOKU / Austria	Central/West Central/West
CM5	2	CREA / Italy SLU / Sweden	South North
CA4/SP3	1	Luke / Finland	North
SP1	1	AU / Denmark	North
SP2	1	INRAE / France	Central/West
DATA 1	1	SLU / Sweden	North
SE2/ INDICATORS1	1	INRAE / France	Central/West
SE4/ INDICATORS 2	1	CREA / Italy	South
POL2/ES7	1	AU / Denmark	North
Total	11		

Table 4: Proposals submitted and validated by the BPM for funding; the type, estimated budget and number of beneficiaries and linked third parties (LTP).

EIP ID	Acronym	Title	Proposal co-ordinator	Type	Budget in kEUR	Number of beneficiaries	Number of LTP	Total number
CM1	MIXROOT-C	Are mixed species systems fostering belowground C inputs and C sequestration?	INRAE / France	medium	1,987	12	3	15
CM1	MaxRoot-C	Optimizing roots for sustainable crop production in Europe – pure cultures and cover crops.	BOKU / Austria	medium	2,000	9	3	12
CM5	AGROECOseqC	AGROECOLOGical strategies for an efficient functioning of plant - soil biota interactions to increase SOC sequestration	CREA / Italy	medium	1,976	7	2	9
CM5	EnergyLink	Linking crop diversification to microbial energy allocation and organic carbon storage in soils	SLU / Sweden	medium	2,000	6	3	9
SP1	SoilCompacC	Mapping and alleviating soil compaction in a climate change context	AU / Denmark	medium	1,997	11	3	14
SP2	EOM4SOIL	External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health	INRAE / France	medium	2,000	10	6	16
DATA1	ProbeField	A novel protocol for robust in field monitoring of carbon stock and soil quality properties based on proximal sensors and existing soil spectral libraries	SLU / Sweden	medium	1,842	9	5	14
SE2/ INDICATORS 1	SERENA	Soil Ecosystem seRvices and soil threats modElling aNd mApping	INRAE / France	large	4,953	14	11	25

EJP ID	Acronym	Title	Proposal co-ordinator	Type	Budget in kEUR	Number of beneficiaries	Number of LTP	Total number
SE4/ INDICATORS 2	MINOTAUR	Modeling and mapping soil biodiversity patterns and functions across Europe	CREA / Italy	medium	2,099	9	6	15
POL2/ES7	Road4Schemes	Roadmap for carbon farming schemes	AU / Denmark	medium	1,847	9	0	9

Each project proposal was briefly described by the applicants; see their summaries below:

CM1 MIXROOT-C: MIXROOT-C project aims to measure in situ root carbon (C) production and to propose root traits related to soil organic C storage in topsoil and subsoil in the context of diversified agrosystems in Europe (e.g. intercropping, grasslands, and agroforestry). The project accounts for the interactions between climate, soil type, above- and belowground plant compartments, plant species and soil C. In order to provide a reliable assessment of belowground C inputs of mixed species systems across Europe and to assess the related co-benefits and trade-offs associated to an increase in root productivity, MIXROOT-C will use complementary approaches, including literature reviewing, collection of existing and new data from long-term field experiments, and process-based modelling.

CM1 MaxRoot-C: To reduce the effect of climate change on food security, carbon farming is indispensable. Mobilizing crop producers to support this transformation requires promotion of cropping systems with equivalent profitability, but higher soil C sequestration. The most viable yet neglected option is through increased and deeper roots of main and cover crops. MaxRoot-C will pioneer assessment methods closing this knowledge gap by providing robust hard data on the root C inputs of main crop varieties and different cover crops across the EU, to determine main drivers and model the C sequestering potential therein. It will provide policy relevant data on which to base future CAP instruments and contribute to the development of future carbon sequestration standards for the EU approved seed lists.

CM5 AGROECOseqC: Soil fauna and microbial communities drive key ecosystem functions, such as nutrient supply to primary production and SOC accumulation. However, plant diversity shapes soil biota composition and activity via rhizodeposition and N-P uptake, microbial symbioses, and trophic cascades. In EU experimental sites network, the project will study how agroecological intensification of cropping systems (e.g. introduction of plant services) can allow better regulation of degradation/resynthesis of soil organic matter and nutrient cycling by the plant-soil system. Advantages and disadvantages of such agroecological systems will be compared to less conservative ones for plant-soil fauna-microbial functional diversity, biomass production, N-leaching, soil C-stable pools, GHG emission and C sequestration.

CM5 EnergyLink: Crop diversification is a potentially attractive agricultural practice for enhancing organic C storage in soils. The aim of EnergyLink is to understand the link between crop diversity and

the processing of organic C by the soil microbiome across a pan-European pedo-climatic gradient. The central hypothesis is that greater crop diversity results in more efficient microbial use of C, thus enhancing the potential of soils to store C. The underlying mechanisms will be elucidated by combining molecular level methods in a bioenergetics framework. Data will inform models describing the turnover of soil organic matter and implement future climate scenarios. The project will provide policy relevant data on which to base future CAP instruments and contribute to the development of carbon farming.

SP1 SoilCompaC: Soil compaction is a major threat to soil productivity and ecological and hydrological soil functioning. Although adverse impacts of compaction on soil properties and functions are relatively well documented, estimates of the extent and severity of compaction in Europe remain elusive, we have limited knowledge on how compaction changes the carbon cycle, and we lack information on compaction risks for different pedo-climatic zones and cropping systems in Europe and how the risks evolve due to climate change. SoilCompaC directly addresses these knowledge gaps. SoilCompaC will quantify interactions between soil compaction and climate, and present information on how to assess, detect, recover and minimize soil compaction, thereby providing a basis for sustainable soil management in Europe.

SP2 EOM4SOIL: EOM4SOIL aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Representative farming systems in Europe (arable crops and vineyards) are selected, taking into account the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. The net budget of soil C storage and greenhouse gas emission including the pre-process step and field application, is assessed as well as the multiple effects of EOM application on soils including contaminants are quantified. Innovative pre-processing are recommended to improve C budget and soil health. The best management practices are defined from scenarios of use assessed with a multicriteria simulation tool, parameterized from long-term experiments.

DATA1 ProbeField: Quick and simple soil analyses directly in the field through proximal sensing has the potential to substantially gear up the number of samples analysed. With focus on visible and near infrared spectroscopy (Vis-NIRS) ProbeField will work to make this happen. The Vis-NIR technique has many advantages required for field analyses of soil properties. There are, however, drawbacks to be overcome. In contrast to spectroscopy in the lab on prepared samples, variable moisture and structure in the field will hamper reliability of analyses. ProbeField will test and suggest physical and mathematical procedure to manage these problems. A wide range of soil properties will be analysed and 3D mapping will be performed to estimate for example carbon stocks. A best practice protocol will be produced.

SE2/ INDICATORS 1 SERENA: The ongoing shift from a merely productive conception of soils towards a more integrative vision of multifunctional soil quality requires a shared analysis of concepts and definitions, and the integration of innovative assessment tools into land planning and soil policies at different scales. SERENA intends to meet these requirements by putting relevant stakeholders at the core of the project, and by providing co-developed indicators and related interpretation values, able to report both on soil degradation and soil-based ecosystem services. Using relevant information on soil quality and soil health, SERENA will jointly evaluate bundles of soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats, and model their evolution depending on climate and management, from the local to the European scales.

SE4/ INDICATORS 2 MINOTAUR: The current status and trends in soil biodiversity across Europe are poorly known, and adequate taxonomical and functional indicators are needed to evaluate the

vulnerability of soils to climate change. MINOTAUR aims to provide models, maps and policy-relevant indicators with validated reference values for monitoring soil biodiversity and associated functions. Moreover, it will aim to understand how agricultural practices can contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation at regional and national levels across the EU. The project will collaborate with relevant EU research projects, international soil biodiversity networks and programs to harmonize and integrate soil biodiversity data and contribute to support long-term harmonized EU soil information and international reporting

POL2/ES7 Road4Schemes: Carbon farming has gained prominence as a mitigation option to reach targets set in the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal. To achieve this, integrating research into policy design and implementation, ensuring mutual benefits for stakeholders, soils and society is helpful. Road4Schemes will (1) assess the strengths and weaknesses of existing and planned schemes for carbon farming and additional Ecosystem Service (ESS) payments, including respective tools for monitoring, reporting and verification; (2) assess stakeholders' perceptions and preferences with respect to strategies for scheme design and policy drivers and barriers; and (3) deliver a roadmap for developing and implementing contextually sensitive result-based schemes for carbon farming and additional ESS payments.

1.2. Eligibility check

Each submitted proposal was evaluated by WP3 against eligibility criteria described in the EJP SOIL's 2nd call, section 3 (D3.4):

- The application must be written in English.
- Applications must be complete and in accordance to the submission procedure.
- Applications must be submitted in time.
- Proposals including beneficiaries and/or third linked parties that are NOT EJP SOIL beneficiaries are not eligible to apply and will be rejected (D3.4).

As mentioned above, all of the 11 proposals passed the eligibility check, but coordinators of selected projects were asked to revise for instance ethics and communication sections prior project start.

1.3. Evaluation results

WP3 built up a pool of external evaluators currently consisting of 28 experts (out of 71 who were invited for the 2nd call) who agreed to evaluate EJP SOIL project proposals and signed a non-disclosure agreement. The evaluators cover multiple disciplines (e.g. soil organic carbon, soil nutrients, agronomy, peat soils, ICT) allowing discipline-specific evaluations. Each project proposal was evaluated by 3 external evaluators. For each proposal, experts presented their evaluation results in an individual evaluation report, explaining the evaluation scores. For each proposal one of the evaluators acted as a rapporteur who assessed all the individual evaluation reports within a call, to: 1) ensure that the evaluator group have been consistent in their evaluations; 2) if necessary, propose a new set of marks or comments; and 3) resolve cases where a consensus could not be reached.

The scoring gives information on the proposals' quality². As mentioned in the EJP SOIL's 2nd call (section 4.4; D3.4) a threshold of 3 out of 5 was applied for each criterion, i.e. proposals with a mean score <3 in any main criterion were not recommended for funding. One of the projects received an average score of <3 for all of the evaluation criteria (i.e. Excellence, Impact, Implementation) and was not recommended for funding.

The request to fund eligible and the highest scoring (in their topic) project proposals was validated by the BPM on 14th of September 2021. MaxRoot-C, EnergyLink, ProbeField, Road4Schemes, SERENA, MINOTAUR and EOM4SOIL were approved for funding without further conditions. Due to the need to balance the EJP SOIL internal budget allocations between the different beneficiaries, other three proposed projects (MIXROOT-C, AGROECOseqC and SoilCompaC) were conditionally approved and were asked by the BPM to revise their budgets, as well as the proposals, according to the evaluator comments. The same evaluators evaluated the three revised proposals, and the BPM validated them for funding on 25th of October 2021.

² **0: Failure:** The proposal fails to address the criterion in question, or cannot be judged because of missing or incomplete information; **1: Poor:** The proposal shows serious weaknesses in relation to the criterion in question; **2: Fair:** The proposal generally addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses that need corrections; **3: Good:** The proposal addresses the criterion in question well but certain improvements are necessary; **4: Very good:** The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but small improvements are possible; **5: Excellent:** The proposal successfully addresses all aspects of the criterion in question.

